

weeds in direct seeded rice more effectively.

A field experiment was conducted during the 1993-94 wet season at the Crop Research Centre, Pantnagar (29 °N, 79 °E, 244 m altitude). Soil is silt loam (Aquic Hapludoll) with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, 0.1 % total N, and CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil. The treatments (see table) were tested in a randomized block design with four replications. Short-duration variety Govind (90 d) was used in 1993 and Saket 4 (110 d) was planted in 1994. Pregenerated seeds were uniformly broadcast in puddled soil at 100 kg dry seeds ha⁻¹ on 10 Jul 1993 and 2 Jul 1994. A single dose of 18 kg P ha⁻¹ and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied along with three splits of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ (1/2 as basal dressing, 1/4 at tillering, and 1/4 at panicle initiation). Soil was kept near saturation during seedling establishment and was later flooded with 0-5 cm water.

Weed samples were taken from a 0.25-m² area and were dried at 70 ± 5 °C. Dry weights were recorded. The common weeds found were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* sp., *Digitaria* sp., *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Commelina henghalensis*, *Casulia axillaris*, and *Eclipta prostrata*. Grain yield was recorded from a 6-m² net plot area. Plant samples from 0.5 m² were taken at harvest to evaluate yield components.

Phytotoxicity problems were not observed in treatments with the new herbicide formulation (herbicides with safener). Weeds were controlled effectively in both years. Pretilachlor + safener at 0.6 kg ai ha⁻¹ applied 3 d after sowing was found most effective in controlling weeds. Yield was statistically at par with that of weed-free check and that of the crop that received two hand weedings. Compared with butachlor- and thiobencarb-treated plots, high plant density with one manual weeding at 30 d was found to suppress weeds significantly (see table). ■

Integrated pest management—other pests

Effect of soil solarization of rice nursery beds to suppress plant parasitic nematodes

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An advantage of solarizing nursery beds, aside from a favorable cost-benefit ratio, is its potential to suppress other soilborne pests besides the target pest. We explored the possibility of using this nonchemical method to suppress plant parasitic nematodes that infect rice seedlings.

Table 1. Effect of solarization and organic amendments on growth characters of rice seedlings. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Length (cm)		Weight [g]	
	Shoot	Root	Shoot	Root
Control	26.20	6.70	0.42	0.165
Solarization	39.30	13.80	1.22	0.631
Organic amendment	38.40	14.80	1.39	0.644
SE ±	1.31	0.78	0.11	ns
LSD (5%)	2.75	1.65	0.23	ns

Table 2. Effect of solarization and organic amendment on population of nematodes infecting rice seedlings. New Delhi, India.

Nematode species	Nematode population 250 cm ³ of soil		Percentage Increase/decrease ^a
	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment	
<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.			
Control	172	250	45.3 (+)
Solarization	115	15	87.0 (-)
Organic amendment	116	33	71.5 (-)
<i>Helicotylenchus</i> spp.			
Control	13	33	153.8 (-)
Solarization	71	30	57.7 (-)
Organic amendment	41	23	43.9 (-)
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i> spp.			
Control	23	40	74.0 (+)
Solarization	61	25	59.0 (-)
Organic amendment	33	22	33.3 (-)
<i>Pratylenchus</i> spp.			
Control	26	45	73.0 (+)
Solarization	37	18	51.3 (-)
Organic amendment	14	7	50.0 (-)
<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>			
Control	105	139	32.4 (+)
Solarization	56	13	76.8 (-)
Organic amendment	78	57	27.0 (-)

^a+ = increase; - = decrease.

The experiment used a randomized block design and was conducted in the IARI farm during the 1995 summer season. The beds were infested with moderate to heavy population of plant parasitic nematodes, mostly root-knot nematodes *Meloidogyne* spp. Tillage was achieved by digging to a depth of about 10 cm, followed by light irrigation. Mulching was done with 60 µm-thick, transparent, white polyethylene sheet buried on all sides. Daily temperature was recorded for each treatment at 0800 and 1500 h for the entire 3-wk duration of solarization and organic amendment treatments. The organic amendment treatment consisted of incorporating mustard cake (0.5% w/w) into the soil 15 d prior to sowing of rice seeds.

At the end of the solarization treatment, polyethylene mulch was removed and soil samples at 0-15 cm depth were drawn. The modified sieving and decanting method by Cobb was used to extract nematodes from 150 cm³ of soil sample.

The nursery beds were loosened and irrigated; seeds of rice cultivar Basmati 370 were then sown. Seedlings were harvested 30 d after sowing and data on plant growth characters and nematode population in the soil were recorded.

Polyethylene mulching increased mean maximum temperature at all observation times (data not shown). An increase of 7-13 °C in the mulched bed over the non-mulched bed was observed during the 3-wk period of solarization. Mulching significantly increased seedling growth (Table 1).

With regard to plant growth parameters, no significant differences were observed between treatments. The improved growth of seedlings in the solarized bed could have been due to the good control of plant parasitic nematodes, other soilborne pathogens, and weeds.

Good control of plant parasitic nematodes (50-87% reduction) was achieved in the solarized beds (Table 3). The decrease in root-knot nematode populations was most notable. Solarization controlled nematodes better than did organic amendment. ■

Water management

Supplemental irrigation for dry seeded upland rice

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Upland rice in Karnataka is often exposed to moisture stress due to dry spells that coincide with the critical growth stages of the crop. Supplemental irrigation using water from small tanks found all over the rainfed rice tract may increase rice yield.

We studied the effect of supplemental irrigation at various growth stages on grain yield of rice during the 1992 and 1994 wet seasons. The experiment consisted of rainfed rice and rice grown with supplemental irrigation (5 cm water depth) at booting, flowering, and grain-filling stages and their combination (see table for treatments). Daily irrigation from booting to 10 d before harvest was also one of the treatments. Due to high percolation in the unpuddled soil, the fields were flooded only for several hours after irrigation or heavy rainfall.

The 5.0- × 3.4-m plots were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Soil was silty clay loam with 0.4% slope. Plots were separated by well-compacted bunds and buffer channels.

Land was plowed and harrowed and direct seeded with rice cultivar Avinash (140 d) at the onset of the rains. A common fertilizer dose (100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 41 kg K ha⁻¹) was applied to all plots.

Total rainfall was 1150 in 1992 and 1135 mm in 1994 with 75 and 79 rainy days during the respective cropping season. Except for a dry spell of 11 d before booting in 1992, good rainfall was received during other stages in both years.

Irrigation at booting, alone or in combination with other stages, relieved the stress caused by the dry spell in 1992 and significantly increased yields. Irrigation only at flowering and grain-filling stages in 1992 and all irrigation treatments in 1994 did not increase yield. This was attributed to sufficient rainfall in 1994. During flowering and grain filling in 1992, plants were not stressed, even without irrigation.

Best results are obtained when timely supplemental irrigation is given only when dry spells occur during critical stages (booting, flowering, and grain filling). ■

Rice yield under sprinkler irrigation

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We investigated rice yield under sprinkler irrigation during three growing seasons 1991-93 in Turkey. The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. Main plots were two irrigation intervals: 4d (A₁) and 8d (A₂). The subplots were irrigation depths (or amount): same amount of pan evaporation (B₁), 50% more than pan evaporation (B₂), and 100% more than pan evaporation (B₃). Plots were 12 m².

Seeds of rice variety Ergene (120 d) were drill-seeded in early May at 180 kg ha⁻¹ using 25-cm row spacing. N (150 kg ha⁻¹) was applied in two splits—1/2 basal and 1/2 60 d after planting. P (35.2 kg ha⁻¹) was applied during soil preparation. Weeds were controlled with two herbicide applications, before drilling and 40 d after drilling. Soil was sandy clay silt with 1.3% organic matter and pH 6.5.

All treatments received similar amounts of irrigation water until seedling emergence to ensure adequate stand establishment. Water use efficiency (WUE) was calculated by dividing grain yield (kg ha⁻¹) by total amount of water applied (mm) for the whole crop.

Irrigation interval has no significant effect on yield (see table). No interaction between irrigation interval and irrigation depth was observed. However, irrigation water depth influenced yield significantly.

As the amount of sprinkler irrigation water decreased, the yield decreased. B₃ had the highest yield while B₂ gave the highest WUE.

Grain yield of rice as influenced by supplemental irrigation management.^a Karnataka, India. 1992 and 1994.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			% increase over rainfed treatment
	1992	1994	Mean	
Rainfed	3.8	5.4	4.6	-
Irrigation at booting	5.3	5.4	5.4	17
Irrigation at flowering	4.4	4.9	4.7	1
Irrigation at grain filling	3.9	5.6	4.8	3
Irrigation at booting and flowering	5.4	5.7	5.5	20
Irrigation at flowering and grain filling	4.2	5.9	5.0	9
Irrigation at booting and grain filling	5.4	5.0	5.2	16
Irrigation at booting, flowering, and grain filling	5.5	5.2	5.3	16
Daily irrigation from booting up to 10 d before harvest	5.2	5.3	5.3	14
LSD (0.05)	1.3	ns ^b		

^a Water depth applied at each irrigation: 5 cm. ^bns = not significant.